

Synthesis, characterization and antimicrobial activity of ruthenium(III), rhodium(III), palladium(II) and platinum(II) complexes with bis(hydroxy-isonitrosobenzoylacetone)thiocarbohydrazone

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The ligand bis(hydroxyisonitrosobenzoylacetone)thiocarbohydrazone (HINBA)₂tcz, has been synthesized by the interaction of thiocarbohydrazone with isonitrosobenzoylacetone in 1 : 2 molar proportion in methanol. Its complexes with Ru^{III}, Rh^{III}, Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} have been prepared and characterized by elemental analyses, magnetic susceptibility, IR, ¹H NMR, spectral data, thermal analysis and electrical conductance measurements.

Isonitrosobenzoylacetone is used as the complexing agent for various metal ions and it predominantly gives coloured complexes with transition metal ions¹⁻³. It is also used for the rapid extraction and spectrophotometric determination of metal ions⁴. Thiocarbohydrazide is useful in analytical chemistry for the identification and estimation of both organic and inorganic compounds⁵. Antitubercular activity of thiocarbohydrazide has been studied *in vitro* against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (BCG strain)^{6,7}. Both the hydrazine groups of thiocarbohydrazide are very reactive and predominantly form bis derivatives with aldehydes and ketones^{7,8}. Metal complexes of β-diketones as well as thio compounds have been widely used in the coordination chemistry due to their versatility and antimicrobial activity⁹.

The present paper, describes the synthesis and characterization of mononuclear Ru^{III}, Rh^{III}, Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} complexes of bis(hydroxyisonitrosobenzoylacetone) thiocarbohydrazone (HINBA)₂tcz derived from condensation of isonitrosobenzoylacetone with thiocarbohydrazone. The preliminary screening of the ligand as well as its metal complexes has been done for antibacterial, antifungal and antitubercular activity.

Results and discussion

The analytical and physical data of the ligand and its metal complexes are given in Table 1. The complexes are insoluble in water and common organic solvents but soluble in DMF, DMSO and chloroform at RT. The analytical data indicate that the complexes have 1 : 1 metal-ligand stoichiometry. The values of molar conductances are in the range

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the ligand and its metal complexes*

Compd./ Empirical formula/ (molecular weight)	Colour	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	Molar conductance Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹
(HINBA) ₂ tcz C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₄ S (452.4)	White	88	183	0.045
[Ru(INBA) ₂ tcz].H ₂ O RuC ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₅ S (569.47)	Red	80	230	0.054
[Rh(INBA) ₂ tcz].H ₂ O RhC ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₅ S (571.31)	Brown	84	220	0.058
[Pd(INBA) ₂ tcz].H ₂ O PdC ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₅ S (574.82)	Brown	83	200	0.053
[Pt(INBA) ₂ tcz].H ₂ O PtC ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₅ S (663.48)	Red	79	136	0.052

*The ligand and all the compds. show satisfactory elemental analyses.

0.052–0.058 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ suggesting non-electrolytic nature of these complexes¹⁰.

Infrared spectra :

The strong bands at 3482 and 3307 cm⁻¹ in the ligand are attributed to the hydrogen bonded ν_{OH} stretching frequency of the oxime group and the stretching vibrations of ν_{NH} respectively¹¹. In the spectrum of the ligand, the strong absorption peak at 1595 and 1507 cm⁻¹ can be ascribed to ν_{C=N} of azomethine and ν_{C=N} of oxime, respectively. The characteristic absorptions of the ligand at 1658 and 1311

cm^{-1} can be assigned to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{S}}$, respectively. In the IR spectra of $[\text{M}(\text{INBA})_2\text{tcz}]\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (where M = Ru, Rh, Pd and Pt), a broad band in the range 3192–3425 cm^{-1} is observed indicating the presence of coordinated water molecule¹². The band in the range 1660–1672 cm^{-1} in the complexes is attributed to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ stretching^{2,12}. The absorption bands in the range 1493–1535 cm^{-1} is attributed to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ of oxime which indicates the possibility of coordination of oximino nitrogen to the metal ion¹³. Shifts in the frequencies of the groups except $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ of azomethine¹⁴ suggest that they are involved in complex formation. The characteristic shift to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{S}}$ mode was observed in the range 1317–1344 cm^{-1} suggests that the thiocarbonyl sulfur is one of the bonding sites. The appearance of 754–760 cm^{-1} ($\nu_{\text{M}-\text{N}}$) and 690–695 cm^{-1} ($\nu_{\text{M}-\text{O}}$) stretching frequencies further confirm the involvement of nitrogen atom of oxime and oxygen atom of carbonyl group in the complex formation. The band observed at 589–595 cm^{-1} are assigned to $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{S}}$ in the metal complexes.

¹H NMR spectra :

The ¹H NMR spectrum of $(\text{HINBA})_2\text{tcz}$ in DMSO-*d*₆ exhibited signal at δ 12.159 which is assigned to the proton (2H) of =NOH group. Aromatic protons (10H) were observed between δ 7.245–7.691 in the ligand. The ligand showed the presence of singlet at δ 9.851 due to -NH (2H) proton. The methyl proton (6H) of ligand was observed at δ 2.167.

The oximino proton was disappeared in $[\text{M}(\text{INBA})_2\text{tcz}]\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (where M = Ru, Rh, Pd and Pt) complexes indicates the proton of the =NOH group is replaced during complexation. The phenyl protons (10H) of complexes are observed as multiplets in the range δ 7.048–7.944. The methyl proton (6H) of the complexes were observed in range δ 1.556–2.313. The NH proton signal is not resolved and not seen in the spectra of the complexes.

Electronic spectra :

The electronic absorption spectrum of $(\text{HINBA})_2\text{tcz}$ display strong band at 28169 and 31746 cm^{-1} due to intra-ligand transition assignable most probably to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ electronic transitions. The electronic spectral bands of Ru^{III} complex in the regions 10330, 16129, 24390 and 35087 cm^{-1} may be assigned to the transitions ${}^2T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{2g}$, ${}^2T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$, ${}^2T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ and $\pi \rightarrow t_{2g}(\pi^*)$, respectively in octahedral field¹⁵. These transition and magnetic value 1.52 B.M. suggest octahedral geometry for the Ru^{III} complex. Rh^{III} complex show diamagnetic nature and electronic spectral bands observed at 10277, 18181, 35714 and 46448 cm^{-1} are assignable to spin allowed transitions ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$, ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$, ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{1g}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{2g}$ which indicate

octahedral geometry¹⁶. The electronic absorption spectrum of Pd^{II} complex showed d-d transition 10526 cm^{-1} and intra-ligand transition (35587 and 45662 cm^{-1}) similarly for Pt^{II} complex showed *d-d* transition 11737 cm^{-1} and intra-ligand transition (35284 and 46728 cm^{-1}). Magnetic moment of Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} complexes exhibit diamagnetic nature which suggest octahedral geometry.

Thermal studies :

Thermal analysis of the complexes shows that they are thermally stable to a varying degree. The complexes show a gradual but insignificant loss in weight up to 100–110° indicating absence of any water of crystallization. The thermal analysis indicates the presence of coordinated water molecule with the central metal ion. The metal complexes initially show the loss of coordinated water in the temperature range 100–240° with further increase in the temperature range investigated, the complexes show decomposition by fragmentation and thermal degradation of organic part of the metal complexes such as CH₂N₄ and C₂₀H₁₆N₂O₄, finally resulting in the corresponding metal sulphides mostly formed above 600°. The result of the thermal studies indicating the presence of one coordinating water molecule in metal complexes.

Antimicrobial studies :

The antimicrobial activities of ligand and complexes were screened against several microorganisms at 200 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. It was evident from the preliminary data that the compounds at screening concentrations used show a strong or a moderate activity against the microorganisms tested.

The ligand shows antibacterial activity against both *S. aureus* and *S. typhi* with MIC value 40 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. The metal complexes of Ru^{III} and Pd^{II} show same MIC value, 40 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ for both the microorganisms, where as Rh^{III} complex shows MIC value 20 and 40 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ for *S. aureus* and *S. typhi* respectively. The metal complex of Pt^{II} shows same MIC value (20 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) for both the microorganisms.

The ligand shows antifungal activity against *Candida albicans*, *T. mentagrophytes*, *T. rubrum* with MIC value 200 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. All metal complexes show moderate antifungal activity with MIC values upto 40 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$.

The ligand shows antitubercular activity against *M. tuberculosis* with MIC value 200 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. The complexes of Ru^{III}, Rh^{III}, Pd^{II} shows MIC value 100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ and Pt^{II} complex show MIC value 20 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. All the complexes were more active than the ligand.

Experimental

The C, H, N, S and metal contents in the complexes

were determined by standard methods. The molar conductances of the complexes were measured in DMF (10^{-3} M solution) on an Elico digital conductivity meter, CM-180. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 1600 FTIR spectrophotometer using KBr pellets. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker AMX-500 spectrometer in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ using tetramethyl silane (TMS) as an internal standard. Magnetic susceptibilities were determined by Gouy's method using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_4]$ as a calibrant. The effective magnetic moments were calculated after diamagnetic correction using Pascal's constants¹⁷. Thermogravimetric studies of the complexes were carried out by recording the change in weight on increasing the temperature from RT to 700° at a heating rate of 10° per minute.

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The C.P. grade chemicals, whenever used, were purified by standard methods. Isonitrosobenzoylacetone^{1(b)} and thiocarbohydrazone¹⁸ were prepared in the laboratory by the reported methods.

Synthesis of bis(hydroxyisonitrosobenzoylacetone)thiocarbohydrazone (HINBA)₂tcz :

The reaction between thiocarbohydrazone (1.06 g, 0.01 mol) and isonitrosobenzoylacetone (3.82 g, 0.02 mol) was carried out in 50 ml methanolic solution, in the presence of trace amount of conc. HCl. The reaction mixture was stirred for one hour at RT. The white product was separated by filtration, and recrystallised from ethanol.

Preparation of complexes : A solution of (HINBA)₂tcz (4.52 g, 0.01 mol in 50 ml of methanol) was mixed with each metal chloride solution (0.01 mol in 50 ml distilled water). The mixture was refluxed for 2 h, cooled and poured on the crushed ice. The coloured compounds (Fig. 1) separated were filtered and washed with distilled water followed by 40% methanol and dried in vacuum.

M = Ru^{III}, Rh^{III}, Pd^{II} and Pt^{II}

Fig. 1. Structural formation of the metal complexes of bis(hydroxyisonitrosobenzoyl acetone)thiocarbohydrazone.

Determination of antimicrobial activity :

The minimum inhibitory concentrations (MIC $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)

of the ligand and complexes were ascertained by using different biological strains such as *S. aureus*, *S. typhi*, *Candida albicans*, *T. mentagrophytes*, *T. rubrum* and *M. tuberculosis* according to the method described elsewhere¹⁹.

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